

Determination of Fluometuron residues in some fodder crops and soil*

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FLUOMETURON (Trade name 'Cotoran') (3-trifluoromethyl phenyl)-1, 1-dimethyl urea) is recommended as a selective herbicide for the control of broad leaved weeds and annual grasses in sorghum, maize, sunflower and wheat grown in heavy soils. The herbicide is sprayed immediately after sowing. Residues of herbicide in the crops and soils need to be determined to ensure the safe limits. Analytical methods for cotoran estimation based on gaschromatographic and spectrophotometric analysis of the herbicide or its hydrolytic products have been described by several workers¹⁻⁶. We report, herein, a simple and quantitative method for the extraction and determination of Fluometuron residues in above crops and soil. The method is based on the quantitative hydrolysis of herbicide into 3-trifluoromethyl aniline (TFA), which on diazotization with nitrous acid and coupling with alkaline β -naphthol solution yields an orange azo-dye. The dye is solubilized in acetone and the colour intensity is measured in a photoelectric colorimeter at 520 nm against 40% aqueous acetone as blank. The amount of TFA, multiplied by the conversion factor 1.44 will give the actual quantity of Fluometuron in the sample. The lower limit of sensitivity of the method has been 0.5 p.p.m.

Materials and Methods

(1) Fluometuron, m.p. 163-164° recrystallized from hexane-acetone (3 : 1) mixture ; (2) 3-trifluoromethyl aniline (TFA), G. R., E. M. (purified by steam distillation) ; (3) sodium nitrite A. R. B. D. H. 3.5% aqueous solution, (4) Aqueous sulphamic acid solution (8%) A. R., B. D. H., (5) Acetone, A. R., B. D. H., (6) β -naphthol G. R., E. M. (100 mg dissolved in 100 ml aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (4%)), A. R., B. D. H., (7) Celite, Johns Manville, (8) Brockmann's neutral chromatographic grade Alumina, E. M.,

(9) Dow Corning Antifoam A ; (10) Anhydrous sodium sulphate A. R., B. D. H ; (11) absolute ethyl alcohol, Bengal Chemicals and Ether solvent (free of peroxide) redistilled ; (12) Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide A. R., B. D. H. ; (13) Photoelectric colorimeter ; (14) Corning Brand Glasswares.

Experimental

Extraction and hydrolysis of fluometuron—Plant material (500-1000 g) was finely ground in a blender and thoroughly mixed with celite (50 g). The pulverized material was packed in a soxhlet extractor and extracted with acetone (1200 ml) for three hours. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. The syrupy extractive was mixed with Dow Corning antifoam (1 ml) to prevent frothing and sodium hydroxide solution (75 ml, 30%). The reactants were refluxed in an oil bath at 160-170° for two and a half hours. The hydrolysate was cooled in an ice bath and transferred to a separating funnel. The reaction flask was thoroughly rinsed with ether and the washings were transferred to the separating funnel. The hydrolysate was extracted with ether thrice (50 ml each time). The ether extract was washed free of alkali and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g).

Chromatographic clean-up—The column (40 x 1.5 cm) consisting of a glass stop-cock was plugged with a pad of glasswool. A slurry of neutral Brockmann's grade alumina (20 g) in ether was poured avoiding any air bubble in the column. The top of the alumina layer was covered with a thin pad of glasswool. The ether extract and its washings were passed through the column, which retained the coloured interferences. The clear eluate was collected in a separating funnel. It was extracted with hydrochloric acid (0.1N) thrice (25, 10 and 10 ml each time). The acidic extracts were taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask, which was gently warmed on a water bath at 40° for 5 minutes to drive off the dissolved solvent and made to volume with HCl (0.1N) (Solution A).

Calibration curve—Estimation of 3-trifluoromethyl aniline (TFA)—100 mg TFA was dissolved in 100 ml of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid (solution 1). 10 ml of solution 1 was diluted to 100 ml with 0.1 N hydrochloric acid (solution 2) and 10 ml of solution 2 was further diluted to 100 ml with 0.1 N hydrochloric acid making the concentration 1 ml = 0.01 mg TFA (solution 3). 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 and 3.5 ml of solution 3 and 2.5, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.5 and 0 ml of 0.1N hydrochloric acid respectively were taken in six boiling tubes. 0.5 ml sodium nitrite solution was added to each tube. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 10 minutes and subsequently 0.5 ml sulphamic acid solution was added to deactivate the excess of unreacted sodium nitrite. After 10 minutes 2 ml freshly prepared β -naphthol solution was mixed in each. The azo-dye so formed was dissolved to a transparent solution by mixing 2 ml acetone. Reaction tubes were constantly shaken for a few minutes after the addition of each reagent. The absorbance was measured in a photoelectric colorimeter at 520 nm against 40% aqueous acetone solution as blank. The absorption of solution

Reactions

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TABLE - SHOWING RECOVERIES OF FLUOMETURON IN FORTIFIED SAMPLES

Crops*	Fluometuron mg	added ppm	Average Fluometuron mg	found ppm	Average recovery percentage
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (cv. M.P. Chari)	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±3 [†]
	0.50	1.00	0.49	0.98	98±4
	1.0	2.00	0.97	1.94	97±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.88	97±3
Maize fodder	0.25	0.50	0.23	0.46	92±5
	0.50	1.00	0.48	0.96	96±3
	1.00	2.00	0.96	0.96	96±3
	2.50	5.00	2.45	4.90	98±4
Sunflower fodder	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±4
	0.50	1.00	0.48	0.96	96±4
	1.00	2.00	0.98	1.96	98±3
	2.50	5.00	2.43	4.86	97±4
Wheat straw	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±3
	0.50	1.00	0.47	0.94	94±5
	1.00	2.00	0.97	4.97	97±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.88	97±4
Soil	0.25	0.50	0.23	0.46	92±6
	0.50	1.00	0.47	0.94	94±4
	1.00	2.00	0.93	1.86	93±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.84	97±4

* Five replicates of 500g each were analysed.

† Standard deviation.

A obtained as above on extraction and hydrolysis of the herbicide was estimated for its TFA content. The amount of TFA could be measured by plotting a graph of concentration of TFA against the optical density thereby calculating the amount of herbicide in the plant material (1 mg TFA = 1.44 mg fluometuron). The recoveries of fluometuron in fortified samples of fodder crops and soil have been shown in the table.

Alternate Procedure—The above method could be applied for the estimation of fluometuron to most of the leafy plant materials and seeds. Riden and Hopkins⁷ in one of the communications have reported that certain halogenated anilines sometimes form complexes with plant constituents and thus are not easily extracted with organic solvents. In such cases, the finely pulverized plant material (500-1000 g) was hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (35%, 3 hrs) and 1 ml Dow corning antifoam under reflux at 170-175° in an oil bath. The hydrolysate was cooled in an ice bath and extracted with ether (400, 400, 200 ml) in a separating funnel. The combined ether extract was washed free of alkali dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to 150 ml. It was subsequently passed through a column (1.5×50 cm) of neutral alumina (40 g) in ether. The eluate was worked out as described above.

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Studies on Isoxazolones. Part IV. Formation Constants of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) Complexes of 3-Phenyl-5-Isoxazolone

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THE use of heterocyclic compounds like pyrazoles, imidazoles etc. and their substituted derivatives as complexing agents are abundant as found in literature¹⁻¹⁰. But there is neither any report on systematic